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THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation: today, during the development of technologies and informatization processes in the world, the issues of reforming preschool education, educating a perfect person, providing them with modern education are the problems that must be solved in the first place. Namely, in the reform of preschool education, it is important and necessary to improve the quality of Education, which is determined by the child's preparation for school.

Keywords: spiritual harmonious personality, upbringing of a harmonious generation, intellectual potential

In this regard, it is important to improve leadership skills in the introduction of modern approaches, management, innovation and information technology into the educational process in preschool educational organizations in ensuring the quality of Education.

Pedagogical and psychological foundations of the activities of the preschool education system, pedagogical conditions for the organization of state and non-state preschool educational organizations and their alternative types, khukukiy-normative foundations of the organization of the activities of preschool educational organizations, the study of world experience in management and technologies for its implementation in the educational process and, on this basis, the implementation of measures

The issue of the formation of a new generation of leaders of the preschool education system is also among the issues of daily relevance. In this case, the recognized functions of the leader about the tasks that must be performed in harmony with the tasks of coordination, planning, regulation, control and evaluation lead to the intellectual maturation of children, the formation of a spiritually competent person and the scientific and spiritual growth of pedagogical personnel, the strengthening of the political and civic position.

The development of innovative processes in local preschool education is reflected in regulatory and software-methodological documents. In this work, a unified educational space was created, with the participation of specialists of all levels of education, the service of methodology, science and practice. The field of preschool education is considered the primary branch of the system of continuing education, which is of paramount importance in all aspects in the upbringing and preparation of the personality of a healthy and harmonious child for school. During the years of independence, the education system and upbringing of a harmonious generation in the Republic rose to the level of the main priorities of state policy. However, the analysis carried out shows that the results and results of the work carried out in the field of preschool education are insufficient.

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In particular, the MTT did not develop modern pedagogical technologies, didactic tasks and developments, modern forms and methods for preparing children for school, the experience of developed countries was not sufficiently analyzed, and, like them, special state educational programs aimed at social, personal, emotional, speech, Mathematical, Physical and creative development, acquaintance with the environment were not implemented, most of the active pedagogical personnel, factors such as the lack of monitoring of the quality of education can be cited.

An important place in this is occupied by the parent, family environment. It is essential that we form in them the skill to know the norm of everything in life and follow it ourselves before the electronic world, which, like a spider web, takes over the world completely, takes over the consciousness of children's minds. Zero does what the child sees, not what he says. Our main goals are to educate high-intelligence people by developing the intelluctive potential of children of preschool age.

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